

**INTERACTIVE DIGITAL ENHANCEMENT
ACTIVITIES IN SCIENCE (IDEAS) AS
REMEDICATION TOOL IN BIOLOGY FOR
IMPROVED PERFORMANCE**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

2023

Volume: 10

Pages: 1020-1029

Document ID: 2023PEMJ923

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8168020

Manuscript Accepted: 2023-18-7

Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) As Remediation Tool in Biology for Improved Performance

Jane Abigail G. Sinampaga*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to develop and validate Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool for Grade 7 students in Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School for the second quarter during the SY 2022-2023. The developed material was evaluated through the adopted Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Printed Materials from the DepEd Learning Resource Management System (LRMDS) based on DM No. 441 s. 2019 in terms of the following criteria: content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, accuracy and up-to-datedness of information that was evaluated by twenty (20) experts, including ten (10) science teachers who have ten (10) or more years of teaching experience in science, five (5) ICT teachers, and five (5) teachers from media team. It was also evaluated by twenty (20) science teachers who have less than ten (10) years of experience teaching science subject. Based on the findings, 2. Both the experts and science teacher respondents evaluated the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool in Biology for grade 7 students with overall weighted mean rating of 3.99 verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory (VS) with respect to content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, accuracy, and up-to-datedness of information. Likewise, the learner's performance greatly advanced after utilizing the developed IDEAS. The respondents remarked that the developed IDEAS, are appealing, interactive, and engaging to the learners with content that is parallel to the learning competencies and objectives. In addition, they stated that the materials have illustrations that are easy to understand; it gives students the chance to explore the content and be engaged in the topics or lessons in a fun way.

Keywords: *remediation tool, student's performance in biology, digital activities*

Introduction

In the Philippines, the spiral curriculum in science presents the concepts and skills in all the branches of science including biology, chemistry, physics, and earth science, with increasing complexity levels from one grade level to another in spiral progression, thus the concrete way to a better understanding of core concepts. The incorporation of science across subjects and other disciplines will lead to meaningful learning in the concepts and their purpose in real-life situations. It is declared in Republic Act 10533 or The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 establishes the new K-12 Basic Education Program of the Philippines that: The State shall create a functional basic education system that will develop productive and responsible citizens equipped with the essential competencies, skills and values for both life-long learning and employment.

Based on the country report conducted by World Bank (2020) for the first time in 2018 the Philippines participated in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). The Philippines ranked last in reading out of 79 participating countries and economies, and second to last in science and mathematics. At least 78 percent of students in the Philippines failed to meet the minimum competency

levels in all three PISA subject, indicating a significant socioeconomic gap. These findings emphasized the critical importance of addressing the quality of basic education. PISA assesses 15-year-olds' attainment and application of critical knowledge and abilities in reading, math, and science. Moreover, the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) results in 2019 revealed that the Philippines only scored 297 in mathematics and 249 in science, which are "significantly lower" than any other participating country in grade 4 math and science according to Mullis, Martin, Foy, Kelly, & Fishbein (2020).

In line with this, it is mentioned in the study of Wu and Xin that (2019) students with poor academic performance have five significant characteristics: low enthusiasm for learning, lack of motivation for learning, lack of interest in learning, weak willingness to learn, and poor learning mentality. To address these issues, some suggestions included strengthening the intervention mechanism through ideals and beliefs education, reforming examination methods, reforming the student status management system, improving the reward and punishment mechanism, strengthening practice links, reforming teaching methods, strengthening education guidance, and improving the independent selection mechanism.

To address the alarming decline in the quality of

Philippine science education, various strategies and interventions are being studied and implemented. In terms of curriculum, the science program advances from traditional methods of instruction toward a more inventive inquiry that focuses on improving students' critical thinking and scientific skills. ICT through digital interactive tools can impact the teaching-learning process as well as students' understanding of the lesson. Likewise, Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) was developed to fill the gaps in learning using a digitally interactive way wherein the students can learn at their own pace while taking into account their needs and the accessibility of materials. Utilizing the potential of technology to enhance teaching and learning processes, activities were designed to work offline using Kotobee Author and Kotobee Reader and operate with gadgets such as mobile phones to reach the most students and stand by the DepEd's tagline that "Nobody will be left behind".

Shifting the lens in the grass root, the increasing number of retained students in Grade 7 of Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School for the past 3 years having 2.08 % or 8 out of 387 students for SY 2017-2018, 3.04% or 13 out of 427 students for SY 2018-2019 and 6.55% or 27 out of 412 students in SY 2019-2020 emphasized that there's a need for immediate solution. Challenged by the data, there were greater attempts to improve students' academic performances as well as their achievements, which amplified the efforts to integrate innovative and effective instruction as a remediation tool to fill in gaps among students that find it hard to cope with the lesson inside the classroom. Thus, the researcher opted to develop Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) and determine its effectiveness as a remediation tool to enhance the academic performance of Grade 7 students since they struggle with understanding Biology.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and validate Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool for Grade 7 students in Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School for the second quarter during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What topics in Biology for Grade 7 could be developed into IDEAS based on the least mastered competencies during SY 2018-2020?
2. What is the evaluation of the experts and science teachers on the developed IDEAS in terms of the following criteria?

- 2.1 Content Quality;
 - 2.2 Instructional Quality;
 - 2.3 Technical Quality; and
 - 2.4 Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information
3. Is there a significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers on the developed IDEAS based on the aforementioned criteria?
 4. What is the level of performance of the learners before and after the utilization of developed IDEAS?
 5. Is there a significant difference on the level of performance of the learners before and after utilizing the developed IDEAS?
 6. What are the comments and suggestions of the experts and science teachers on the developed IDEAS?

Literature Review

With DepEd's battle cry "Sulong Edukalidad" to address the challenge of quality basic education there is really a need to intensify the teaching learning process by filling the gaps among students through the conduct of intervention and remediation. According to Department of Education (DepEd) Memorandum No. 013 series of 2018, remedial is any form of organized instructional interventions given to a learner to address his or her learning gaps or subject area deficiency. The 2030 Sustainable Development Goals emphasize quality education because the global community believes that everyone has the right to a high-quality education, with the goal of ensuring inclusive and equitable education and encouraging lifelong learning opportunities for all. The Philippine educational system also aspires to provide every student with an inclusive and high-quality education. As a result, Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act 2013, was enacted in order to implement the K-12 curriculum and enhance the competitiveness of Filipino students and graduates.

To address gaps in teaching science innovation is really necessary. Motivation is a must to help students relearn topics and concepts which they find hard to understand. Batuyong and Antonio (2018) state in their journal that Science and technology contribute to the achievement of sustainable development goals. Science, according to the 2002 Basic Education Curriculum, aims to help every Filipino learner gain a functional understanding of scientific concepts and principles as they relate to real-life situations, as well as the scientific skills, attitudes, and values needed to analyze and solve day-to-day societal problems. Learners can gain these scientific abilities most effectively by incorporating Information and Communication Technology (ICT). In this regard,

according to Tabassum (2018), computer-assisted education is an interactive instructional strategy in which a computer is used to provide the instructional content and monitor the learning that occurs. Furthermore, it incorporates text, pictures, audio, and videos into the learning process. Computer-Assisted Instruction, also known as CAI, is the use of a computer as a tool to facilitate and improve instruction. CAI programs deliver subjects via tutorials, drill and practice, simulation, and problem-solving methodologies, and they test students' understanding.

Likewise, Eckhardt and Harms (2018) stated that scientific discovery learning with computer simulations leads to the acquisition of intuitive knowledge. The results demonstrated the efficacy of these instructional interventions on learners' intuitive knowledge acquisition. A predetermined combination of instructional support for data interpretation and for self-regulation proved to be successful for learners' intuitive knowledge acquisition after a learning session involving the computer simulation. Furthermore, instructional intervention describing and interpreting own simulation outcomes for data interpretation seems to be an effective method for acquiring intuitive knowledge. Hero, Dela Cruz, Paz, and Caparas (2021) conducted a study entitled "Integration of E-Learning System and Its Effect to the Study Habits and Participation of Junior High School Students" examined and extrapolated the integration of e-learning system and its correlation to the Junior High School students' study habits and participation. The respondents consist of one hundred and twelve (112) Junior High School students in one private school in the district of Obando, Bulacan, Philippines. The findings of the study were attained through a descriptive-correlation method that gives a result indicating that E-learning system is functional, reliable, usable, and efficient having a strong link or a significant correlation between the integration of the E-learning system and students' study habits and participation.

Furthermore, Eviota and Boyles's (2022) study, entitled "Least Learned Competencies in Grade 9 Biology: Basis for Development of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM)," aimed to create Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) in Biology for Grade 9 students. It determined the least learned competencies in Grade 9 Biology. It also evaluated the created materials' quality in terms of content, format, presentation, organization, accuracy and up-to-datedness. The teachers' and experts' evaluations of the materials' quality were compared. The materials'

quality was also compared in terms of the four aspects. The produced SIM demonstrated six identified competencies in Grade 9 Biology class, and its quality is extremely excellent in terms of content, format, presentation, organization, accuracy, and up-to-datedness. There is no significant difference between teacher and expert assessments of the SIM's quality.

Methodology

The study utilized a descriptive, and quasi-experimental research design to develop and validate Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science IDEAS as a remediation tool to improve the performance of students in Grade 7. Pandey, P., and Pandey M. (2021) defined descriptive research as methodologies of investigation based on firsthand observation of a phenomenon or a systematic collection of data from a population through personal contact and interviews. Descriptive research is concerned with acquiring information about current events or occurrences in order to describe and interpret them. This research approach entails more than just gathering and tabulating data; it also requires accurate analysis, interpretation, comparisons, and the identification of trends and linkages. Questionnaires, tests, interviews, checklists, rating scales, and observation are examples of data collection instruments. On the other hand, a quasi-experimental design, according to Thomas (2020), seeks to establish a cause-and-effect link between an independent and dependent variable. In general, the dependent variable is measured twice: once before and once after the treatment is performed. The pretest-posttest design is similar to a within-subjects experiment in that each participant is tested under both the control and treatment conditions. If the average posttest score is higher than the average pretest score, it is reasonable to conclude that the treatment is responsible for the improvement.

Participants of the Study

The IDEAS were evaluated and validated by 20 experts, including 10 science teachers who have 10 or more years of teaching experience in science, 5 ICT teachers, and 5 teachers from the media team. It was also evaluated and validated by 20 science teachers who have less than 10 years of experience teaching science subjects. Student respondents were chosen and identified using the result of the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of the second periodical test. Forty-eight (48) students in Grade 7 of Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School participated in the study.

Instruments of the Study

The researcher adopted the Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Printed Materials from the DepEd Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) based on DM No. 441 s. 2019 to evaluate and validate the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS). The evaluation tool was composed of four (4) major sections: Content Quality, Instructional Quality, Technical Quality, and Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information. In addition, the result of the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) was used to identify the students who will undergo remediation. Pretest and posttest were adopted from the standardized second quarter examination provided by DepEd Baras' central office following the Table of Specification (TOS) anchored in PIVOT 4A Budget of Work Manual (BOW) of DepEd Calabarzon. To test the level of effectiveness in enhancing students' levels of academic performance, a pretest and posttest were administered to grade 7 who obtained the lowest Mean Percentage Score (MPS).

Procedure

Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) was validated and evaluated by following the step-by-step procedure. First, the researcher used the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) provided by DepEd when creating the Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool to improve the performance of Grade 7 students. Next, the researcher asked permission to conduct the study from the Division Superintendent and School Principals. Upon approval, in the evaluation and validation process, the researcher adopted the Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Printed Materials from the DepEd Learning Resource Management System (LRMDS) based on DM No. 441 s. 2019. The IDEAS were evaluated and validated by twenty (20) experts and twenty (20) science teachers. After the periodical examination was administered the researcher coordinated with the science department chairperson to have the copy of consolidated test result for the second quarter. At this point, the researcher coordinated with the science teacher of the section which had the lowest Mean Percentage Score (MPS). Parent consent was prepared as approved by the school principal. Upon approval it was distributed to the student respondents. Forty-eight (48) Grade 7 Hyacinth students participated in the study. Finally, the data gathered from the validation, evaluation, pretest, and posttest were then collected and tabulated using the prescribed statistical tool to

determine the digital interactive material's effectiveness in improving the level of performance of students and the significance of the difference.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher herself explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. She ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

Topics in Biology for Grade 7 Developed into IDEAS based on the Least Mastered Competencies During SY 2018-2020

The least mastered competencies in Biology for Grade 7 in school years 2018–2020 were included in the table. With a frequency of 49% and below, correct responses were considered unmastered topics, 50%–74% were nearing mastery, and 75%–100% were considered mastered topics

The average frequency of correct responses over the two school years shows that the competency that deals with the process of fertilization under the topic of Reproduction ranks first among the least mastered competencies, and all of the other competencies were identified as nearing mastery.

In line with this, with a significantly low level of mastery among other competencies, it was put into consideration to include all the topics and competencies for the second quarter, which include Microscope, Biological Organization, Cell, Reproduction, and Interaction, in the development of Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS).

Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) in Terms of Content Quality, Instructional Quality, Technical Quality and Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information

Table 1. Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS0 in Terms of Content Quality)

Content Quality	Expert		Science Teacher	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Content is accurate.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Content is up-to-date.	4.00	VS	3.90	VS
Content is logically developed and organized.	3.95	VS	3.95	VS
Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.95	VS	3.85	VS
Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.99	VS	3.97	VS

It is shown in the table that, with respect to content quality, the overall evaluation of the experts and science teachers on the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool for Grade 7 received a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating with an overall weighted mean rating of 3.99 from the experts and 3.97 rating from science teachers.

This implied that the material contains appropriate enhancement activities that will help supplement learners' understanding and are aligned with the learning standards and competencies prescribed in the curriculum. Likewise, the rating suggests that the developed material needs to consider adding more activities that incorporate more content relevant to real-life situations.

It can be gleaned from the table that experts and science teacher respondents agreed that in terms of instructional quality, the developed materials had an overall weighted mean of 3.99 from the experts and 3.98 from science teachers with verbal interpretation of Very Satisfactory (VS). However, the rating also suggests that the remediation material can still be improved to effectively stimulate creativity and effectively employ feedback on the responses of the target user of the developed material and maximize its full potential.

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS0 in Terms of Instructional Quality)

Instructional Quality	Expert		Science Teacher	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Purpose of the material is well defined.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Material achieves its defined purpose.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	4.00	VS	3.95	VS
Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.95	VS	3.95	VS
Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	4.00	VS	3.90	VS
Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3.95	VS	4.00	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.99	VS	3.98	VS

Likewise, based on the evaluation of experts and science teachers, the developed material can effectively stimulate the creativity of the target users, making it enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS0 in Terms of Technical Quality)

Technical Quality	Expert		Science Teacher	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	4.00	VS	3.95	VS
There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	3.95	VS	4.00	VS
Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.95	VS	4.00	VS
Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	3.95	VS	4.00	VS
Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
The user support materials (if any) are effective.	3.90	VS	4.00	VS
The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.95	VS	4.00	VS
The material can easily and independently be used.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
The material will run using minimum system requirements.	4.00	VS	3.95	VS
The program is free from technical problems.	3.95	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.97	VS	3.99	VS

As reflected in the table, the experts and science teacher respondents both rated the developed digital interactive remediation tool, in terms of technical quality a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating having 3.97 from the experts and 3.99 from science teachers which implied that the developed IDEAS had been constructed to be engaging and had utilized appropriate audiovisual elements, system requirements, and other technical aspects for a smooth flow of ideas. Also, other technical issues can still be improved to help learners focus on the task and learn effectively with an appropriate medium of instruction suited to their needs which was free from technical problems.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) in Terms of Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information

Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of information	Expert		Science Teacher	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Conceptual errors.	4.00	NP	4.00	NP
2. Factual errors.	4.00	NP	4.00	NP
3. Grammatical and / or typographical errors.	4.00	NP	4.00	NP
4. Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.).	4.00	NP	4.00	NP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.00	NP	4.00	NP

It can be gleaned from the table that conceptual errors, factual errors, grammatical and / or typographical errors, and other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.) all gained an overall weighted mean of 4.00 as rated by the experts and science teachers with a verbal interpretation of Not Present (NP). This means that the developed materials are free of errors and contain valid and up-to-date information, which will be useful in understanding the contents of the material accurately and effectively.

Summary on the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS)

Table 5. Summary on the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS)

	Expert		Science Teacher	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Content Quality	3.99	VS	3.97	VS
Instructional Quality	3.99	VS	3.98	VS
Technical Quality	3.97	VS	3.99	VS
Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information	4.00	NP	4.00	NP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.99	VS	3.99	VS

As reflected in the table, the experts rated the material's content quality at 3.99, while science teachers rated it at 3.97 with verbal interpretation of Very Satisfactory (VS). Likewise, based on the instructional quality of the material, experts rated it 3.99 and the science teachers rated the material 3.98, which was verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory (VS). Similarly, experts and science teacher respondents rated the material as Very Satisfactory (VS) in terms of technical quality having 3.97 rating from the experts and 3.99 rating with science teachers. Lastly, for accuracy and up-to-datedness of the material which include conceptual errors, factual errors, grammatical and/or typographical errors, and other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.) obtained a rating of 4.00 from both experts and science teachers with verbal interpretation of Not Present (NP).

Therefore, the overall evaluation of the experts on the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool in Biology for Grade 7 with respect to content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information which include conceptual errors, factual errors, grammatical and/or typographical errors, and other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.), obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.99, which is verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory (VS). The result implies that the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) passed all the needed criteria which may serve as a vital learning and remediation tool intended to achieve the learning standards, competencies, and outcomes prescribed in the DepEd curriculum.

Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS)

Table 6. Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) in Terms of Content Quality

Content Quality	Mann-Whitney U	Z-value	Z-critical	Decision	Interpretation
Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content is accurate.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content is up-to-date.	180.00	0.076	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content is logically developed and organized.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content is relevant to real-life situations.	180.00	0.149	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant

The table shows the result of the Mann-Whitney U Test. The computed z-value of 0.000 in indicators 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10, a z-value of 0.076 in indicator 4, and a z-value of 1.149 in indicator 8 with a degree of freedom of 38, is less than the z-critical value of 1.960 at 0.05 level of significance, which means that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers in the given criterion.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was failed to reject, and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers, which was Very Satisfactory (VS) in terms of the indicators of content quality used to evaluate the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool in Biology for Grade 7.

This means that the two groups of respondents agreed that the developed material is acceptable for the subject and grade level for which it was designed, as well as whether it is compatible with the subjects covered by the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).

Table 7. Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) in Terms of Instructional Quality

Instructional Quality	Mann-Whitney U	Z-value	Z-critical	Decision	Interpretation
Purpose of the material is well defined.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Material achieves its defined purpose.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	180.00	0.076	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant

As reflected in the table, the computed z-value of 0.000 in indicators 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, and 9, a z-value of 0.158 in indicators 4 and 10, and a z-value of 0.076 in indicator 8 with a degree of freedom of 38, is less than the z-critical value of 1.960 at the 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers in the given criterion. Therefore, the null hypothesis was failed to reject and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers, which was Very Satisfactory (VS) in terms of the indicators of instructional quality used to evaluate the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool in Biology for Grade 7.

This implies that both groups of respondents agreed that the material's goal was clearly stated. (i.e., implicitly or explicitly defined), and the material achieves its defined purpose; the level of difficulty is suitable for the intended target user; graphics, colors, and sounds are used for the proper instructional purposes.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) in Terms of Technical Quality*

Technical Quality	Mann-Whitney U	Z-value	Z-critical	Decision	Interpretation
Audio enhances understanding of the concept. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed. The user support materials (if any) are effective. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material. The material can easily and independently be used. The material will run using minimum system requirements. The program is free from technical problems.	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	200.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	190.00	0.158	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant

It can be gleaned from the table that the computed z-value of 0.000 in indicators 1, 5, 6, 8 and 13, a z-value of 0.158 in indicators 2,3,4,7,10,11,12 and a z-value of 0.076 in indicator 9 with a degree of freedom of 38, is less than the z-critical value of 1.960 at the 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers in the given criterion.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was failed to reject, and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers, which was Very Satisfactory (VS) in terms of the indicators of technical quality used to evaluate the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool in Biology for Grade 7.

This suggests that the two groups of respondents agreed that the developed material has an effective integration of audiovisual material as well as the usage of appropriate system requirements to assist students in learning the topic in a more engaging manner.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) in Terms of Up-to-Datedness of Information*

Technical Quality	Mann-Whitney U	Z-value	Z-critical	Decision	Interpretation
Content Quality	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Instructional Quality	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Technical Quality	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant
Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of Information	200.00	0.000	1.960	Do not reject H ₀	Not Significant

The table revealed that the computed z-value of 0.000 in all the indicators with a degree of freedom of 38, is less than the z-critical value of 1.960 at the 0.05 level of significance, which means that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers in the given criterion. Therefore, the null hypothesis was failed to reject, and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of experts and science teachers in terms of the indicators under accuracy and up-to-datedness of information used to evaluate the developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a remediation tool in Biology for Grade 7.

This indicates that both respondents agreed that the material is free from all errors such as conceptual, grammatical, factual, computational, typographical, and other minor errors (for example, inappropriate or unclear illustrations, missing labels, wrong captions, and others) and obsolete information.

Level of Performance of the Learners Before and After Utilizing the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a Remediation Tool in Biology for Grade 7

Table 10. *Level of Performance of Grade 7 Students Before and After Utilizing the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a Remediation Tool in Biology for Grade 7*

Score	Description	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
40-50	Outstanding	4	8.33	24	50.00
30-39	Very Satisfactory	13	27.08	19	39.58
20-29	Satisfactory	17	35.42	3	6.25
10-19	Fair	13	27.08	2	4.17
0-9	Poor	1	2.08	0	0.00
Total		48	100.00	48	100.00
Weighted Mean			13.42		19.79
Standard Deviation			9.65		8.63
Interpretation			Satisfactory		Outstanding

The table shows the frequency of scores of Grade 7 students' pretest and posttest, as well as the equivalent description. Based on the table, only 4 out of 48 students, or 8.33%, received an Outstanding (O) performance in the pretest; 13 received a Very Satisfactory (VS) performance with 27.08%, 17 received a Satisfactory (S) performance with 35.42%, 13 got a Fair (F) performance with 27.08%, and 1 obtained a Poor (P) performance with 2.08%. After the remediation, the posttest results demonstrated an improvement in the learners' performance, particularly those who had Outstanding (O) ratings that increased from 4 to 24 students, or 50%. This shows that the learners' performance greatly advanced after utilizing the developed IDEAS.

Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Learners Before and After Utilizing the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a Remediation Tool in Biology for Grade 7

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Learners Before and After Utilizing the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as a Remediation Tool in Biology for Grade 7*

	N	Mean	Sd	Computed t-value	Critical value	Decision	Interpretation
Pre-test	48	25.60	9.65	16.398	1.679	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Post-test	48	38.42	8.63				

It can be gleaned from the table that the total computed t-value of 16.398 with a degree of freedom of 47 is greater than the critical value of 1.697 at 0.05 level of significance based on the administered pretest and posttest. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it can be inferred from the table that there is a significant difference in the learners' level of performance in terms of the administered pretest and posttest before and after using the Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS). Since the mean score in the posttest is 38.42, which is higher than the mean score in the pretest, which was only 25.60, this suggests that the learner's performance improved after using the remediation tool.

Respondents' Comments and Suggestions on the Improvement of the Developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) as Remediation Tool in Biology for Grade 7

The developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) took into account and considered the suggestions and recommendations given by the experts and science teacher respondents who evaluated the materials in terms of the criteria used to evaluate the material.

In terms of content quality, it was suggested to add features of Tagalog translation in each direction and activity for the learners to be able to understand the activities well. Moreover, in terms of instructional quality, the experts and science teacher respondents pointed out that testing the effectiveness of the said digital enhancement activity should be extended to other places, including a more heterogeneous group of learners. Moreover, in terms of technical quality, experts and science teacher respondents mentioned inserting background music, if possible, on selected contents like videos because background music has a beneficial influence on cognitive performance that will increase the ability to reduce stress and improve learners' mood.

The respondents remarked that the developed IDEAS, are appealing, interactive, and engaging to the learners with content that is parallel to the learning competencies and objectives. In addition, they stated that the materials have illustrations that are easy to understand; it gives students the chance to explore the content and be engaged in the topics or lessons in a fun way.

Conclusion

Based on the presented findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: (1) Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) could be developed based on the least mastered competencies of the students. (2) The developed Interactive Digital Enhancement Activities in Science (IDEAS) conformed to the criteria of instructional material development set by LRMDs guidelines in terms of content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information. (3) The Grade 7 student's level of performance improved after the developed IDEAS was utilized.

In view of the conclusions stated in this study, the following were hereby recommended: (1) Parallel studies may be conducted utilizing the interactive digital as a remediation tool in other subject areas. (2) Future researches may be conducted utilizing other variables, wider scope, and large number of learners to

measure the performance with the use activities as Interactive Digital Remediation tool. (3) Other interactive supplementary material can be developed using other platforms accessible to learners.

References

Batuyong, C. T., & Antonio, V. V. (2018). Exploring the effect of PhET® interactive simulation-based activities on students' performance and learning experiences in electromagnetism. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(2), 121-131.

Eckhardt, M., Urhahne, D., & Harms, U. (2018). Instructional support for intuitive knowledge acquisition when learning with an ecological computer simulation. *Education Sciences*, 8(3), 94. doi:10.3390/educsci8030094

Eviota, M. P., & Boyles, L. Z. (2022). Least learned competencies in grade 9 biology: Basis for development of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM). *Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 53-70.

Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., Kelly, D. L., & Fishbein, B. (2020). TIMSS 2019 International Results in Mathematics and Science. Retrieved from Boston College, TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center. Retrieved from <https://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2019/international-results/>.

Pandey, P., & Pandey, M. M. (2021). Research methodology tools and techniques. Bridge Center.

Republic act no. 10533 govph. (2013, May 15). Retrieved from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republic-act-no-10533/>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jane Abigail G. Sinampaga

- Marikina Polytechnic College – Philippines
- Baras-Pinugay Integrated High School - Philippines